

Errata and Addenda for “Pathfinding for Triple-Axis Spectrometers” (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5092159)

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December 20, 2021

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- Many thanks to A. Filhol for producing a signed *MacOS* package of the software, which can be downloaded from <http://www.ill.eu/tas-paths> (also thanks for setting up the website).

November 17, 2021

- References to source code directories and files are given relative to the *project root path*, which is under `taspaths/` inside the source code archive and at <https://code.ill.fr/scientific-software/takin/paths> for the repository.

November 16, 2021

- The dissertation, Ref. [1], should more strictly be designated as “doctoral thesis”, not as “PhD thesis”.

November 10, 2021

- Info: Demonstration videos for the pathfinding software can be found here: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCzhvfui0jVYvvxGdm3v9q4A/videos> .

October 14, 2021

- Info: The three utility programs described in chapter 8.1 (“Test tools”) can be started from the *Tools* menu in the main software’s GUI.

October 13, 2021

- Further infos for the binary versions of the software: The *MacOS* version is unsigned, to start it for the first time, hold *Control* while clicking on the application icon. The *MinGW* version for *Windows* is a test build and does not have the full performance of the *MacOS* or *Linux* versions.

October 12, 2021

- Further info for chapters 1 and 2: The wavenumbers of the incoming and outgoing neutron beams, k_i and k_f , are related to their respective wavelengths, λ_i and λ_f , via $k_{i,f} = 2\pi/\lambda_{i,f}$, see, e.g., Ref. [2, p. 66].

October 8, 2021

- Forgot to thank Alain Filhol in the “Acknowledgements and Thanks” chapter on p. 9 (sorry Alain!). He has always helped me with all things *Mac* since the *Takin* software, especially concerning application directory layout, application packaging, *Info.plist*s, and with the build scripts. The build scripts and general purpose code in the present software are based on their counterparts from the *Takin* and *tlibs* software [3, 4, 5].

October 7, 2021

- Addendum for chapter 2, pp. 23-24 of the thesis: The important thing about these calculations is that they are all performed in crystal space using the metric tensor, even though some equations are written in lab/instrument space for simplicity.
For example, the wavenumbers Q in equations (2.30) and (2.35) are implicitly understood to be calculated as $Q = \sqrt{Q_i^{\text{rlu}} Q_{\text{rlu}}^i} = \sqrt{g_{ij} Q_{\text{rlu}}^i Q_{\text{rlu}}^j}$, i.e. using the covariant dot product [6, p. 808] for the vector length. Equally, the wavevectors $|Q\rangle$ in equations (2.36)-(2.39) are understood to be given in crystal space, i.e. $|Q\rangle = |Q_{\text{rlu}}\rangle$.
See here for an implementation in *Python* and here (function: `calc_tas_a3a4`) for an implementation in *C++* of the formalism.
- Note again that – as mentioned in the thesis – chapter 2 had already been published previously in my physics doctoral thesis [1, pp. 139-143] and in the software from Ref. [3].

October 6, 2021

- Chapter 2 of the thesis presents the formalism for calculating the fractional crystal coordinate UB matrix (section 2.1) and from that the triple-axis angles (section 2.2). The original presentation of both these calculations, namely Ref. [7], was only cited for section 2.1, but should also be cited for section 2.2 of the thesis.
- Typo on page 19, second paragraph: “these formula” → “these formulas”.

October 5, 2021 (updated November 17, 2021)

- Missing info in the `readme.txt` of the supplementary files: The *tlibs2* library, which is included in the source code archive under sub-directory `./tlibs2` (or `<archive>/taspaths/tlibs2`), is **not** part of the present thesis, as it has already been developed during my physics doctoral thesis [1] and its further developments have also already been published in several papers [3, 4, 5, 8].

References

- [1] T. Weber, *Dynamics at the Orbital Ordering Phase Transition in MgV_2O_4 and at the Ferromagnetic Phase Transition in $MnSi$* . Doctoral Thesis, Technische Universität München, Physikdepartment E21, Munich, Germany, 2017. ISBN: 978-3-843-93114-4. URL: <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn/resolver.pl?urn:nbn:de:bvb:91-diss-20170320-1339645-0-4>.
- [2] R. Gross and A. Marx, *Festkörperphysik*. Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag GmbH, Rosenheimer Str. 145, 81671 Munich, Germany, 2012. ISBN: 978-3-486-71294-0.
- [3] T. Weber, “Update 2.0 to “Takin: An open-source software for experiment planning, visualisation, and data analysis”, (PII: S2352711016300152),” *SoftwareX*, Volume 14, Page 100667, 2021. ISSN: 2352-7110. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2021.100667>.
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- [5] T. Weber, R. Georgii, and P. Böni, “Takin: An open-source software for experiment planning, visualisation, and data analysis,” *SoftwareX*, Volume 5, Pages 121–126, 2016. ISSN: 2352-7110. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2016.06.002>.
- [6] T. Arens, F. Hettlich, C. Karpfinger, U. Kockelkorn, K. Lichtenegger, and H. Stachel, *Mathematik, 3. Auflage*. Springer-Verlag GmbH Berlin Heidelberg, Germany, 2015. ISBN: 978-3-642-44919-2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-44919-2>.
- [7] M. D. Lumsden, J. L. Robertson, and M. Yethiraj, “UB matrix implementation for inelastic neutron scattering experiments,” *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, Volume 38, Number 3, Pages 405–411, 2005. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0021889805004875>.
- [8] T. Weber, D. M. Fobes, J. Waizner, P. Steffens, G. S. Tucker, M. Böhm, L. Beddrich, C. Franz, H. Gabold, R. Bewley, D. Voneshen, M. Skoulatos, R. Georgii, G. Ehlers, A. Bauer, C. Pfeleiderer, P. Böni, M. Janoschek, and M. Garst, “Topological magnon band structure of emergent Landau levels in a skyrmion lattice,” 2021. Submitted, in review.